

Skin Disease Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— Screening for skin diseases is the identification of risk factors for the skin. It helps you know how dangerous your condition is and you can take precautions accordingly. This research describes the prediction of skin diseases using the decision tree. Diagnosing and predicting skin diseases is a lengthy process because it requires a patient history, physical examination, and appropriate laboratory diagnostic tests. Diagnosis and prediction of disease become difficult as the complexity and number of disease features increases. For this reason, a computer-aided diagnosis and recognition system is introduced. This algorithm contains some steps involving data set analysis, data pre-processing and data classification which was implemented with the help of a classifier like decision tree. The algorithm compares the test and training data set for skin disease detection. The system will bring more precision and efficiency, making it more reliable for dermatology.

Keywords—skin disease, skin diagnosis, Machine Learning, Decision Tree

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin disease is recognized as a medical condition associated with a particular set of symptoms. Diseases can be classified based on the amount of area of the body it affects. Systemic diseases affect the entire body and disseminated diseases spread to different parts of the body. Skin disease is a condition that affects the skin of the human body. It has a serious impact on people's health. This is widespread and therefore there is a need for effective remedies. The detection of skin diseases is very important as it can cause serious losses to people. In today's world, we need an automated diagnostic system to help us diagnose diseases faster, it reduce the manual effort and time required to detect diseases. Some skin diseases are benign, while others have serious consequences. Many rare skin diseases are passed down from generation to generation. Bacteria get trapped in the pores and hair follicles, which is one of the main causes of skin diseases. Skin diseases can be caused by certain lifestyle factors.

The common causes of skin diseases are:

- Genetic Contact with allergies and other people's skin

- Fungi or parasites that inhabit the skin.
- Viruses and sun Burn

The symptoms of skin disease vary greatly depending on the conditions you have. Diseases aren't always the cause of skin changes. For example, wearing shoes that don't fit your body can cause blisters. However, if unexplained skin changes occur, they may be related to the underlying medical condition. You can also reduce skin symptoms by changing your lifestyle.

- Avoid or limit certain foods, such as sugar and dairy products, if your doctor recommends it.
- Coping with stress, Practice proper hygiene, including proper skin care.
- Excessive alcohol consumption and smoking should be avoided at all costs.

Our proposed system is based on a decision tree, which is a deep learning algorithm that helps detect skin disease prediction. Decision Tree is a machine learning technique that can perform classification, regression, and multiple outcome tasks. These are powerful algorithms that fit complex data sets. There are two types of decision trees, one is used for classification and the other is used for regression.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

- In[1]NareenO.M.,Salim&AdnanMohsin,Abdulazeez"Human Diseases Detection Based On Machine Learning Algorithms" examines certain machine learning techniques used in healthcare applications in order to provide acceptable decision support. The goal of this work is to reduce the research gap in developing a practical decision support system for medical applications
- .In[2]ChithambaramT,LogeshKannan"Heart Disease Detection Using Machine Learning" We can detect cardiac disease using several types of parameters in the dataset. The major goal of the study is to improve the accuracy of heart-disease detection utilising algorithms in which the target

output counts whether or not a person has heart disease.

- In[3]Prof .Shrikant Sanas(Guided) , Prabhakar Pawale1, Gaurav Ghadage2, Monish Sahani"SKIN DISEASE PREDICTION"describes skin disease prediction by using a neural network based on image analysis.
- In[4]Marouane Fethi Ferjani"Disease Prediction Using Machine Learning" By the evaluation of performance measures, recognise trends among various types of supervised ML models in illness detection. The most widely discussed supervised machine learning algorithms included Nave Bayes (NB), Decision Trees (DT), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)
- In [5] Pravin S. Ambad & A. S. Shirsat et al. "An examination of an image "A method to detect skin disorders" has proposed a statistically based technique for early detection of skin problems. Their research was particularly concerned with the application of statistical analysis and correlation algorithms to detect skin cancer indications early.

III.MOTIVATION

Skin disease is a major global health problem that affects many people. Due to the rapid development of technology in recent years and the application of various data mining techniques, the progress of dermatological predictive classification is more and more predictive and accurate. Therefore, there is a need to develop machine learning systems that can accurately classify skin disorders. Machine learning techniques that have been used to predict skin conditions are superior to all other techniques..

IV. METHODOLOGY

- The purpose of this work is to build a model that is used for the prevention and early detection of skin diseases.
 - An application is built where a person can upload a csv file, then the data will be sent to the trained model.
 - The model analyzes the csv file and detects the disease that person had.
 - Our system will use a decision tree to train the skin disease data.
 - We compiled our dataset by collecting datasets from different skin disease-specific websites that Includes disease details used for testing and training.
 - It also used to assess accuracy.
 - Finally predicts the disease after evaluating
- **Dataset Analysis:** The dataset used in this study is taken from Google. Briefly, this data set was formed

to examine skin diseases and classify the type of diseases. This data set contains 7 skin diseases. These seven classes of skin diseases include C1: fungal infection, C2: allergy, C3: chicken pox, C4: dengue fever, C5: acne, C6: psoriasis, C7: impetigo.

- **Data preprocessing:** The methodology proposed in this study is based on data preparation. A data-driven strategy is included in the data preprocessing step to select patient records and important variables for analysis. This was used to perform normalization.
- **Training data:** The algorithm's learning experience is based on the training set's observations. In supervised learning problems, each observation has one or more observed input variables and one or more observed output variables.
- **Test data:** A test set is a collection of data that is used to assess the model's performance using a performance metric. It's necessary that no observations from the training set make the test set.

Proposed System Flowchart

V.MODEL BUILDING

The model building is the main step in skin disease prediction. We build the model using decision tree.

Importing libraries

Pandas ,Numpy, Matplotlib, OpenCV, Flask, Seaborn, and other Machine Learning libraries are defined as an interface of a set of rules or efficient functions built in a particular language to conduct repetitive work such as arithmetic computation, visualizing datasets, reading photos, and so on.

Importing dataset

